

A Study on Financial Performance of MSME

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ABSTRACT

There is a great potential for employment in the MSMEs business in India. The MSMEs sector's primary goal is to enable people to work for themselves, which contributes either directly or indirectly to the growth of the country. The MSMEs sector is generating revenue and wealth for the country by manufacturing a range of goods that are sold to other nations, earning foreign income and reducing the need for imports. Although this industry is expanding impressively, issues with marketing, funding, infrastructure, and technology are hurting the industry as a whole. All other issues are mostly being caused by finance issues, which are placing a heavy load on MSMEs and making it impossible for them to sustain the market.

The government, financial institutions, MSMEs development institutions, and development organisations must support this venture if the "Make in India" tagline is to be successful. The ministry must conduct more EDPs, promote credit assistance opportunities for this industry, and educate MSME entrepreneurs. This sector needs to receive hassle-free loans from financial institutions if it is to significantly contribute to GDP development. Eventually, the economy will grow, a large number of individuals will become self-employed, and they will in turn create a large number of jobs.

KEYWORDS: *Financing Performance, Financial Problems, MSMEs, Financial Sustainability.*

INTRODUCTION

Many people find work in the MSMEs sector, which inspires young businesspeople to launch an enterprise with only a minimal investment. According to numerous studies, MSMEs play a significant role in the growth of developing economies, make a significant contribution to that development, and benefit their individual economies greatly. The country gains the following benefits.

A vast network of more than 32 million businesses, providing almost 70 million individuals with jobs low start-up costs for new businesses, producing a wide range of more than 6000 goods, Do not need an expensive infrastructure, MSMEs do not need advanced technologies, generating wealth and income to support greater living standards, limiting the movement of individuals between different locations, fostering more balanced growth and reducing regional imbalances, utilisation of raw materials from the area properly, considerable GDP contribution for the improvement of the country, export marketing,

Providing a source of foreign currency and easing the burden of imports.

Major MSMEs in Karnataka State

The MSMEs industry in the state of Karnataka has enormous potential. This industry supports a large number of individuals and is increasing the number of independent contractors in this state. The following are important MSMEs in the state of Karnataka. Textile, food processing, mineral, wood, engineering, chemical, jewellery, plastics, rubber, electronics, electrical, paper products, and printing.

Financing Problems of MSMEs

The most important factor in running any organisation is money. It is the lifeblood of the company, lubricating each of its functional divisions and ensuring that it remains in good shape. Similar to how a person collapses when their blood flow ceases, a business too comes to a halt when its financial resources run out, ultimately causing an organisation to fail. Any business depends on its financial stability.

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Businesses require funding to continue their expansion and growth-related operations. Some business plans, effective production, and marketing requirements all rely on funding.

Finance Purpose for MSMEs

MSMEs require financing to maintain a successful firm. Production, generating consumer demand, increased business infrastructure development, modern technology advancement, innovation, creativity, and modernization.

Financing Problems of MSMEs

Finance is a necessary for every firm at all stages of ongoing operations, but for MSMEs, obtaining financing is the biggest challenge. The issues with financing are the root of all other issues because so many business transactions depend on it. As a result, finance is the driving force behind how businesses are operated. The study's primary focus is on MSMEs' finance issues, which reveal how they impair their ability to sustain their financial health. Lack of appropriate and timely credit availability is among MSMEs' financing issues. restricted access to equity capital, demand for collateral the excessive interest rate, rising costs for raw resources, Lack of working capital, increased power costs, increased labour rates, The decrease in sales volume and the rise in bad debts, transportation costs, rent, goods and service taxes (GST), government taxes, and customs duties, Changing prices for gasoline and diesel, rising insurance premiums, and a delay in collecting accounts.

Statement of the Problem

MSMEs are regarded as being the foundation of the Indian economy. However, the largest barrier to the development of this industry is a lack of funding. Every phase of the business lifecycle requires the use of finance as a major input. A key requirement for MSMEs is adequate financial sources. The lack of sufficient progress is a result of numerous issues, particularly financial ones. An economic assessment recently indicated that finding finance sources is the biggest challenge for both registered and unregistered sectors, adding to the stress of managing the firm. For creating the new function, a need analysis has been done.

Since money is the lifeblood of MSMEs and a necessity for all of their business activities, financing issues are therefore having a significant negative impact on these companies. Due to the dependence of all business activities on financing, MSMEs require additional funding to maintain improved financial sustainability. MSMEs' funding issues could involve issues with debt or equity financing. The researcher concentrated on the financing issues facing MSMEs

in the state of Karnataka because it is quite difficult for MSMEs to timely obtain finance from a variety of sources for their better finances. There is a need to research the financing issues MSMEs are facing and how they are affecting their businesses. All of the reports indicated that MSMEs have financial issues, but what are these issues? The researcher sought to identify each financial issue and determine how it affects the sustainability of MSMEs.

Significance of the Study

The MSME sector in India contributes significantly to industrial output, generates jobs, and is a major driver of GDP. Finance is a crucial engine for MSMEs' business success. All other issues are a result of inadequate funding, which is also required for both early and late growth. Due of the higher risk, financial institutions only have a limited specialisation in this industry. According to a 2012 IFC report, the overall financing deficit in the MSMEs sector is expected to be 650 billion dollars. Only until the government and other financial institutions take the initiative to provide loans for this sector will the industry flourish, adding to wealth and employment. Consequently, research into the financial issues and opportunities facing MSMEs is necessary.

Scope of the Study

Based on surveys, the study's primary focus is the manufacturing sector of MSMEs, namely three sectors: the textile, mineral, and wood industries. Both registered and unregistered micro, small, and medium-sized businesses were considered. It discussed the funding issues facing MSMEs and how these affect their capacity to sustain their financial health.

Literature review

In their 2010 study, **Grimsholm and Poblete** concentrated on both external and internal factors that influence the expansion of SME in Thailand. Competition, trade restrictions, and a lack of skilled workers were discovered to be the main culprits. A study was then done by **Shivani Mishra** (2012) to "emphasise the role MSME plays in the promotion of the socially disadvantaged group and also focused on the position of MSMEs in the backdrop of globalisation." After 2009, the MSME sector's growth began to decelerate, according to a Ministry of MSME (2013) publication. It suggested doing and growing businesses, supporting entrepreneurs, etc." The effects of globalisation on the growth of the MSME sector as well as the elements affecting Indian MSMEs were underlined by **Arati Deveshwar** (2014). She came to this conclusion because research on a few growth indicators from the pre- and post-

globalization periods shows that the expansion of MSMEs in terms of units, employment, production, and export has been negatively impacted by globalisation. In his research, **Khurud** (2015) investigated "how the elimination of protective measures affects the sector's exports of MSMEs. The results indicated that MSME exports grew in comparison to India's overall exports once the protective measures were lifted. **Gade** (2018) made an effort to investigate "the role of MSMEs in the development of India. For the industry to maintain its contribution to the growth of the country, he focused on the areas that need to be strengthened. He discovered that the MSMEs might be the country's blessing and best hope for the future. According to **Boateng et al.** (2019), "51% of the Indian MSMEs operate from rural areas, compared to 49% from urban centres. About 40% of all jobs in the nation are

attributed to this industry. While 45% of these newly produced jobs come from rural areas, 55% are located in metropolitan areas. 76% of these are men, while 24% are women. The importance of MSMEs in India was discussed by **G SudhaVenkatesh and Muthaiah** Understanding the significance and contribution of MSMEs in India is the study's key goal. Only secondary data from a separate source was used by the writers. In 2013, **Dr. P. Uma:** The MSME sector is the answer to increasing GDP growth, creating more jobs, and reducing poverty. The importance of MSMEs to India's economic development was stressed in the study. She talked on rural MSMEs and their advantages and disadvantages, such as flexible owner management and affordable labour. The only secondary data used by the author.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative research technique based on several in-depth interviews with three (3) lecturers from the National Economics University and University of Labour and Social Affairs who had substantial experience in accounting in MSMEs. These are Bangalore's top two institutions for teaching accounting and finance. Three (3) other experts who work as chief accountants for MSMEs were also questioned at the same time. The interview topics were centred on MSMEs' characteristics related to financial performance.

This research has identified the financial performance of MSMEs (FP) in four (4) attributes as presented in Table 1

Table 1. Financial Performance Attributes of MSMEs

Financial performance of MSMEs(FP)	
CODE	SCALE
FP1	The profit of the company has increased in the last three years
FP2	The number of the asset (property) of our company has increased in the last three years
FP3	The number of working capital has increased in the last three years
FP4	The number of sales growth has increased in the last three years

Quantitative Research Methodology

For this study, a questionnaire with four factors and a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 for "strongly disagree" to 5 for "strongly agree" was created. The survey method was used to gather data from a variety of accountants in MSMEs in Bangalore. A total of 150 questionnaires were distributed, and 120 respondents returned the completed forms with all the necessary information for data entry and analysis. The size of this sample was in line with a 1998 study by Hair et al., which found that the research sample needed to be at least five times as large as the total number of scale indicators. Four (4) indicators were included in the questionnaire for this study; hence a minimum sample size of $4 * 5 = 20$ observations must be obtained. Then, using SPSS23, the data from these 120 questionnaires was cleaned, coded with the information requested in the questions, and inputted.

1. Descriptive statistics,
2. Cronbach's Alpha assesses the reliability of the scale, and
3. Independent t-test and ANOVA.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 displays data collection information. It reveals that out of the 120 responders, around 26.7% were men and 88 (73.3%) were women. Of these, 75 (or 62.5%) are under the age of 27, while 37.5% of the participants were beyond the age of 27. The respondents were divided into three groups: accounting staffs (45.8%), general accounting (27.5%), and head accountants (26.7%; 32 respondents). 53.3% of those who participated in the study had job experience of 5 years or less, while 46.7% had work experience of more than 5 years. 38 respondents representing 31.7% of the sample, worked for MSMEs in the manufacturing and construction sectors, and 82 others representing 68.3% of the sample worked for commercial and service organisations.

Table2.Demographic Response

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender			
Male	32	26.7	26.7
Female	88	73.3	100.0
Age			
To 27 years old	75	62.5	62.5
Over27yearsold	45	37.5	100.0
Job description			
General accountants	33	27.5	27.5
Chief accountants	32	26.7	54.2
Accounting staff	55	45.8	100.0
Work experience			
To5years	64	53.3	53.3
Over5years	56	46.7	100.0
Business areas			
Industry and construction	38	31,7	31,7
Commercial and service	82	68,3	100,0
Total	120	100.0	

Table 3 then shows that the respondents agree with the dependent variables of "Financial performance of MSMEs," where four traits had average ratings that were quite high when compared to the highest rating on a Likert 5-point scale, at 3.827 and 3.827, respectively. The average rating for all four characteristics was 3.783 or above.

Table 3. Descriptive Analysis of Attributes of Financial Performance of MSMEs

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std .Deviation
FP1	120	2.0	5.0	3.800	.6559
FP2	120	2.0	5.0	3.783	.6634
FP3	120	3.0	5.0	3.875	.5433
FP4	120	3.0	5.0	3.850	.5599
Valid N (listwise)	120			3.827	

Cronbach's Alpha

The Cronbach's Alpha test has been used to gauge the financial success of MSMEs. Table 4 below shows the results of evaluating the Cronbach's alpha of several qualities. The findings also demonstrate that Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for attributes of the dependent variables are greater than 0.6 and that all attribute correlation coefficients are higher than 0.3. Consequently, each of the dependent variables' characteristics is statistically significant (Hair et al, 2010; Hoang & Chu, 2008).

Table4. Results of Cronbach's Alpha Testing of Attributes

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items			
.746	4			
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
FP1	11.508	1.781	.376	.717
FP2	11.525	1.562	.523	.603
FP3	11.433	1.996	.378	.710
FP4	11.458	1.881	.441	.670

Independent T –TEST

Table 5 shows a comparison of the findings from the assessment of the financial performance of MSMEs between participants with fewer than five years of work experience and those with more than five years. The results of Table 5's data indicate that Sig= 0.335, which is higher than 0.05. The difference between the two job experience categories 5 years or less and over 5 years is same. Additionally, Sig value T-Test = 0.043 0.05 indicates that the level of financial performance of MSMEs resulting from these various work experiences differs in a statistically significant way (Hair et al, 2010; Hoang & Chu, 2008).

Table 5. Differences of financial performance of MSMEs between Participants 5 years or less work experiences and over5years work experiences-Independent Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper	
FP	Equal variances assumed	.938	.335	-2.050	118	.043	-.15681	.07648	-.30826	-.00535
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.046	114.84	.043	-.15681	.07664	-.30862	-.00499

Table 6 compares the findings of the assessment of the financial performance of MSMEs between participants who worked for industry and construction businesses and those who worked for commercial and service businesses. Table 6's findings indicate that Sig Levene's Test is 0.213, which is higher than 0.05. There is no distinction between the two types of businesses—commercial and service enterprises and industry and construction enterprises. Additionally, T-Sig Test's value was 0.793, which is greater than 0.05, indicating that there isn't a statistically significant difference between the financial performance of MSMEs from these various business categories (Hair et al, 2010; Hoang & Chu, 2008).

Table 6. Differences of financial performance of MSMEs between participants work for industry and construction enterprises and commercial and service enterprises-Independent Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper	
FP	Equal variances assumed	1.567	.213	-.263	118	.793	-.02198	.08345	-.18723	.14327
	Equal variances not assumed			-.280	83.836	.781	-.02198	.07865	-.17839	.13442

ANOVA

To compare the findings of the evaluation of the financial performance of MSMEs among the three subjects—accounting staff, general accounting, and head accountant an ANOVA test was required. Table 7 demonstrates that the Sig of 0.811 is greater than 0.05, indicating that the homogeneity variance among the variable value groups (various job descriptions) hypothesis has not been disproved. There is no statistically significant difference in the level of financial performance of SMEs between the three groups of job descriptions, as shown in Table 8 by the value of Sig. = 0.127, which is greater than 0.05. (Hair et al, 2010; Hoang & Chu, 2008).

Table7: Test of Homogeneity of Variances

FP			
Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
.210	2	117	.811

Table8: ANOVA

FP					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.739	2	.369	2.097	.127
Within Groups	20.611	117	.176		
Total	21.349	119			

However, actual survey results and in-depth interviews in qualitative research show that the financial performance of MSMEs has not met the managers' expectations and that the majority of the managers of this group of companies have little to no financial knowledge. This is true even though the results of quantitative research have shown positive financial performance of MSMEs. In addition, MSMEs, of which there are many naturally occurring small and micro firms, make up the majority of businesses in Bangalore. The majority of these companies' managers and directors likewise have only general education backgrounds in finance, business administration, and economics. Therefore, short-term courses and training programmes that are appropriate for MSME managers should be offered by training institutes.

Managers will gain additional knowledge to help them make judgments that will increase the effectiveness of financial performance through these training sessions.

MSMEs must estimate their revenue goals with complete information, such as projected sales volume, expected selling price, and anticipated customer credit policy. Managers will then have access to sufficient data to make informed business decisions.

The qualities of the budgetary aim may have a positive and notable impact on things like the growth of sales revenue, the growth of profit, and managerial performance. In order to improve company performance, managers should concentrate on creating budget targets that are more precise, challenging, and attainable (Le & Nguyen, 2020).

FINDINGS SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The study uses a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative research. Qualitative Research: In-depth interviews with three (3) lecturers and three (3) chief accountants from Bangalore. This method found that MSME managers have little to no financial knowledge, and the companies' financial performance does not meet expectations. Quantitative Research: A survey of 120 accountants from MSMEs in Bangalore using a questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale to measure four financial performance attributes (FP1-FP4): profit, assets, working capital, and sales growth.

- Descriptive Statistics (Table 3): The average rating for all four attributes was high, with a mean of 3.827, suggesting that respondents agreed that financial performance had increased.
- Reliability Analysis (Table 4): The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.746 confirms the reliability

of the measurement scale, as it is above the 0.6 threshold.

- Independent T-test (Table 5): A significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was found in financial performance based on work experience, with those having more than 5 years of experience perceiving a different level of performance.
- Independent T-test (Table 6): No significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was found in financial performance between different business areas (industry/construction vs. commercial/service).
- ANOVA (Table 8): No significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was found in financial performance among different job descriptions (accounting staff, general accountants, chief accountants).

The Paradoxical Conclusion

- The study highlights a discrepancy between the quantitative and qualitative findings. The high mean scores from the quantitative survey indicate a general agreement among accountants that MSMEs' financial performance has improved.
- However, the qualitative interviews paint a different picture, citing a lack of financial knowledge among managers as a key reason for poor performance. The researchers resolve this paradox by prioritizing the qualitative findings, suggesting that the quantitative survey results may not reflect the actual financial reality of the businesses, but rather the perceptions of the accountants surveyed.

Recommendations

Based on the qualitative findings and the overall conclusion, the study makes several recommendations to improve the financial performance of MSMEs:

- Mandatory Training: Training institutes should offer short-term courses and training programs tailored for MSME managers to enhance their financial knowledge.
- Informed Decision-Making: Managers need to estimate revenue goals with complete information, including projected sales volume and pricing, to make informed business decisions.
- Precise Budgeting: Managers should focus on creating specific, challenging, and attainable budget targets to positively impact business performance.

MSMEs produce nearly one million new employments annually, employ up to 51% of the work force, and produce more than 40% of the nation's GDP. Even though there are a lot of MSMEs, the most of them are underdeveloped and operate on a

small scale (Le & Nguyen, 2020). The study of financial performance in Bangalore MSEMs has significant theoretical and practical implications given the current state of affairs.

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